

Statement

Inclusive AI: The Need for a Global Strategy to Prevent Widening Inequality

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When discussing Artificial Intelligence (AI), most events and guidelines tend to fall into two broad categories. One focuses on AI from a technical perspective, covering aspects such as AI models, performance improvements, and advancements in machine learning. The other addresses the ethical and regulatory dimensions, emphasizing responsible AI use, ethical considerations, and policy frameworks. The Paris AI Action Summit 2025 was no exception to this divide, with both its sessions and its key outcomes, such as the Statement on AI¹ and the Paris Charter on AI in the Public Interest, reflecting these two overarching aspects.

However, an important topic that is often overlooked is the need for a coordinated approach between governments, AI developers, and international organizations that can bridge the accessibility gap and prevent AI from reinforcing existing inequalities.

While principles such as openness and accessibility are frequently emphasized in AI guidelines, they are often framed in a narrow context. Discussions on openness in AI typically center on open models and open-source AI, with the assumption that making AI open-source naturally ensures accessibility. However, this assumption does not hold true on a global scale.

There are several reasons that prevent global access to AI. One main reason is political and regulatory barriers. Sanctions and geopolitical restrictions can limit access to AI models, datasets, and platforms, preventing certain countries or regions from benefiting. Another reason is infrastructure and resource constraints. Many regions lack the computational power, internet connectivity, or skilled workforce needed to effectively use AI technologies.

Consequently, such limitations and wide gaps not only deepen the AI divide but also raise ethical concerns. AI systems developed without considering these accessibility challenges cannot truly serve people, the planet, or the public interest.

To bridge this gap, we need a mutualized approach to AI development, ensuring that ethical AI is not just a regional or corporate initiative but a truly global endeavor. We need a global strategy for AI accessibility, a common knowledge representation and shared data sources.

Without these efforts, AI will continue to reflect and amplify existing inequalities rather than serving as a tool for collective progress.

¹ <https://www.elysee.fr/en/emmanuel-macron/2025/02/11/statement-on-inclusive-and-sustainable-artificial-intelligence-for-people-and-the-planet>